

Parallelizing N-Body Simulations: HPC with Forward Euler Method

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The gravitational N-body problem, with its computational complexity of $O(N^2)$, presents significant challenges for large-scale simulations. To tackle these challenges, this study implemented and evaluated various optimization strategies on multi-core CPUs, including compiler flags, auto-vectorization, OpenMP multi-threading, and MPI parallelization. Among these, OpenMP delivered the most notable performance improvements for single-node setups. While MPI can show potential in distributed computing environments, its effectiveness in this study was limited by communication overhead. A hybrid MPI-OpenMP approach failed to deliver additional benefits, likely due to resource contention. As a result, shared-memory parallelism using OpenMP was identified as the most effective method for single-machine simulations. Future efforts should focus on optimizing distributed MPI, exploring advanced algorithms like hierarchical methods, and refining parallelization techniques to achieve better scalability and efficiency for larger and more complex N-body simulations.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background of the N-Body Problem

The N-body problem models the motion of N celestial bodies interacting via gravitational forces. The non-linear and chaotic behaviour of a system for $N > 2$ makes analytical solutions infeasible.[1, 2] Numerical methods, such as Forward Euler, approximate trajectories but demand substantial computational resources.[3]

1.2 Objectives and Scope

The research focuses on designing and developing an optimized C++ application for simulating the N-body problem using the Forward Euler method for celestial body trajectory calculations. It then aims to identify the most effective optimization technique among several approaches, including compiler-level optimizations, OpenMP-based multi-threading, SIMD (Single Instruction, Multiple Data) parallelism, MPI (Message Passing Interface) distributed computing, and hybrid methods that combine these techniques.

The optimizations are tailored for CPU-based computations, with performance evaluations conducted on a 13th Gen Intel Core i5-13420H processor (see Table 7 in Appendix for detailed specifications). Execution times are measured for varying problem sizes to assess the impact of each optimization. GPU acceleration and advanced numerical integration techniques are deliberately excluded from the scope, with the primary objective being to maximize efficiency within a CPU-centric computational framework.

2 Methodology

2.1 Serial Implementation

The serial version of the N-body simulation calculates gravitational interactions iteratively, updating the positions and velocities of celestial bodies. Initial conditions for masses, positions, and velocities are generated randomly using normal distributions to mimic realistic scenarios. At each discrete time step, gravitational forces

between all pairs of bodies are computed using nested loops based on Newton's law of gravitation. The velocities are updated using the equation $F = ma$ and the positions are subsequently adjusted based on these updated velocities.

The simulation runs until the defined total simulation time is reached. Optional 3D scatter plots illustrate the initial and final positions of the bodies, aiding in result interpretation. Dynamic memory allocation is used to handle arrays for storing body attributes, ensuring efficient memory utilization. These arrays are deallocated at the simulation's conclusion to prevent memory leaks.

2.2 Optimisation Techniques

2.2.1 Compiler Flags. To optimize the N-body simulation, the following GCC compiler optimization levels were tested: $-O0$, $-O1$, $-O2$, and $-O3$. These levels progressively apply more aggressive optimizations, with $-O3$ enabling advanced features such as function inlining and automatic vectorization. To specifically isolate the effect of auto-vectorization, the $-fno-tree-vectorize$ flag was used alongside the flags to explicitly disable vectorization. This setup served as a baseline for comparing performance against manually implemented SIMD (Single Instruction, Multiple Data) parallelism.

Additionally, architecture-specific optimizations were applied using the $-march=native$ flag, which takes advantage of CPU-specific features to maximize efficiency. These compiler-level optimizations resulted in substantial performance improvements and provided a solid foundation for subsequent parallelization strategies, including multi-threading and distributed computing.

2.2.2 OpenMP Multi-Threading. OpenMP pragmas were utilized to parallelize the N-body simulation, focusing on computationally intensive sections while maintaining correctness. Initialization loops for mass, position, and velocity were executed serially, as their runtime impact was minimal. In the main simulation loop, independent iterations in the force reset and position/velocity update steps were parallelized using `#pragma omp parallel for`[4].

Parallelizing the gravitational force computation presented challenges due to concurrent writes to the shared force array. Three solutions were explored to address this issue:

- **Atomic Directives:** Thread-safe updates were enforced using `#pragma omp atomic`. While this approach maintained correctness, frequent synchronization caused significant performance degradation due to contention.
- **Critical Sections:** The `#pragma omp critical` directive serialized access to shared data, ensuring correctness. However, it introduced severe bottlenecks, particularly as thread counts increased.
- **Reduction Clause:** A custom reduction operation was implemented to aggregate forces efficiently. This approach

minimized synchronization overhead and offered better scalability compared to atomic or critical methods.

```
#pragma omp parallel{
  #pragma omp for reduction(+:force[:N][:3])
}
```

To further optimize parallel performance, various scheduling strategies, such as static and dynamic scheduling, were evaluated for their effectiveness in load balancing. Additionally, the number of threads was adjusted using the `OMP_NUM_THREADS` environment variable to identify the optimal configuration for the simulation workload and system architecture.

2.2.3 SIMD Parallelism. Single Instruction, Multiple Data (SIMD) parallelism was employed to enhance computational throughput by leveraging vector registers. `#pragma omp simd` directives were applied to the force reset and position/velocity update loops, successfully accelerating these independent computations through vectorized execution.

Efforts to apply SIMD to the gravitational force computation were hindered by data dependencies, nested loops, and irregular memory access patterns. While the `-O3` compiler flag enabled auto-vectorization, the observed performance gains were negligible compared to the results with `-fno-tree-vectorize`, highlighting SIMD's limitations for memory-bound tasks with high data dependencies.

```
#pragma omp parallel for simd schedule(static)
for{
  update position and velocities
}
```

In summary, SIMD significantly improved performance in independent loops but was constrained in computations with complex dependencies and irregular memory access.

2.2.4 MPI Implementation. The Message Passing Interface (MPI) was employed to distribute the computational workload of the N-body simulation across multiple processes, enabling efficient parallelism. The master rank (rank 0) initialized the masses, positions, and velocities of all bodies and broadcasted these arrays to all ranks using `MPI_Bcast`, ensuring consistent initial conditions.

Gravitational force calculations were distributed among processes by assigning each process a unique subset of pairwise interactions.[5] Each process handled a fraction of the outer loop over all bodies, with subsets determined by rank. For body i , the inner loop over j started at $i + \text{rank} + 1$ and incremented by $\text{size} - 1$, where size is the total number of processes. This approach avoided redundant calculations and ensured balanced workloads.

```
for (int i = 0; i < N; i++) {
  for (int j = i + rank + 1; j < N; j += size - 1) {
    }
}
```

```
}
```

Only the master rank updated the velocities and positions of bodies after force computations. These updates were synchronized across ranks using `MPI_Bcast` to prepare for the next simulation iteration.

Key MPI functions included `MPI_Init`, `MPI_Comm_rank`, `MPI_Comm_size`, `MPI_Bcast`, and `MPI_Finalize`. By distributing the workload and eliminating redundant computations, the MPI-based approach significantly enhanced computational efficiency.

2.2.5 Hybrid Implementation (MPI and OpenMP). A hybrid MPI and OpenMP approach was tested to combine distributed and shared memory parallelism. On an 8-core system, 8 MPI ranks used OpenMP threads for additional parallelism. However, resource contention, synchronization overheads, and core oversubscription hindered performance, making the hybrid setup less effective than standalone MPI. Simpler methods like standalone MPI or OpenMP proved more efficient for the tested hardware.

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Performance Metrics

3.1.1 Execution Time (T_{exec}). Measured in seconds to evaluate performance across optimization levels (`-O0` to `-O3`) and vectorization.

3.1.2 Speedup (S). Performance gain over baseline (`-O0`), calculated as:

$$S = \frac{T_{exec, baseline}}{T_{exec, optimized}}$$

3.1.3 Efficiency (E). Resource (Thread/Ranks) utilization, defined as:

$$E = \frac{S}{N_{resources}}$$

3.1.4 Scalability. Performance variation with increasing problem size (N) and time steps (T).

3.2 Baseline Performance

The baseline performance was evaluated under various GCC optimization levels (`-O0`, `-O1`, `-O2`, `-O3`) for execution time and speedup. Results were analyzed with and without vectorization.

Vectorisation Disabled. Execution time decreased significantly from `-O0` to `-O1`, with diminishing gains at higher levels. For $N = 900$, $T = 2000$, a 79.5% reduction was achieved (269.98 s to 55.29 s). Speedup peaked at $6.45\times$ (`-O2`), with minor drops at `-O3`.

Vectorisation Enabled. Vectorization provided modest improvements (2%-8%), with the highest gains (12.6%) for $N = 500$, $T = 50$ at `-O3`. Speedup peaked at $1.14\times$, with minimal benefits for larger problem sizes.

Defining the Baseline. The baseline performance was defined as the best runtime for each problem size using `-O3` optimization with auto-vectorization:

Problem Size (N)	Final Time (T)	Run ID	Run Time (s)
1000	100	7	2.628
500	50	14	0.341
900	2000	18	41.377

3.3 Performance Within Optimisation Techniques

Compiler Optimisation. As discussed in the previous section, compiler optimizations significantly enhanced the performance of the N-body simulation. The $-O1$ optimization level yielded the most substantial gains, primarily due to basic techniques such as loop unrolling and constant folding. Speedups of up to $4.88\times$ were observed for $N = 1000$ and $N = 900$, while $N = 500$ achieved $4.66\times$. Higher optimization levels ($-O2$ and $-O3$) provided diminishing returns, with incremental improvements of approximately $1.02\times$ for larger problem sizes, indicating a performance plateau.

Fig. 1. $-O1$ yields maximum gains

Fig. 2. Auto Vectorisation has little impact on execution time

Auto-vectorization further reduced execution times by 2%-8%, with a peak speedup of $1.14\times$ for $N = 500$ under $-O3$. For $N = 900$, the impact of auto-vectorization was minimal ($1.02\times$), largely constrained by the complexity of nested loops and inherent data dependencies.

In summary, while $-O1$ effectively addresses fundamental inefficiencies, additional performance improvements beyond this level require manual code restructuring or the adoption of more efficient algorithms.

OpenMP Threading with SIMD. The N-body simulation shows significant performance improvements with increasing thread counts:

- For $N = 1000, T = 100$: Execution time decreased from 0.738 s (2 threads) to 0.395 s (4 threads, $\sim 46\%$ reduction) and further to 0.342 s (8 threads, $\sim 13\%$ additional reduction). Beyond 8 threads, performance plateaued, with a slight increase to 0.349 s at 12 threads.
- For $N = 900, T = 2000$: Execution time dropped from 11.797 s (2 threads) to 6.448 s (4 threads, $\sim 45\%$ reduction) and marginally to 6.136 s (8 threads, $\sim 5\%$ additional reduction). Beyond 8 threads, performance stabilized at 6.050 s with 12 threads.

These results indicate that OpenMP achieves optimal performance with 8 threads, fully utilizing the system's physical cores. Beyond this point, hyper-threading inefficiencies and synchronization overhead negate further gains, underscoring the importance of balancing parallelism with system constraints.

Fig. 3. Execution Time significantly decreases with > 2 threads

MPI. The N-body simulation shows significant performance gains with increasing MPI ranks up to an optimal threshold, beyond which communication overhead begins to dominate.

- For $N = 1000, T = 100$:
 - Execution time decreased from 1.317 s (2 ranks) to 0.493 s (4 ranks, $\sim 62.6\%$ reduction).
 - Further reduction was observed at 8 ranks, reaching 0.469 s ($\sim 4.9\%$ additional improvement).
 - Beyond 8 ranks, performance degraded, increasing to 0.897 s at 12 ranks due to communication overhead.
- For $N = 900, T = 2000$:
 - Execution time dropped from 21.746 s (2 ranks) to 8.087 s (4 ranks, $\sim 62.8\%$ reduction).

- Increasing to 8 ranks resulted in a slight increase to 9.117 s, while 9 ranks achieved the best performance at 7.519 s.

These results emphasize the trade-off between parallel efficiency and communication overhead in MPI. The optimal number of ranks depends on the problem size, with 8 ranks being optimal for $N = 1000$, $T = 100$, and 9 ranks for $N = 900$, $T = 2000$.

Fig. 4. Execution time improves with more than 2 ranks but rises after 4 due to communication overhead.

4 Comparative Analysis

4.1 Serial vs. Parallel Performance

To compare serial and parallel implementations, we analyzed execution times for the N -body simulation for $N = 1000$ and $N = 900$. The baseline is the best serial execution time: 2.628 s (Run 7, $N = 1000$) and 41.377 s (Run 18, $N = 900$). The results for OpenMP and MPI parallelizations are summarized below.

4.1.1 OpenMP Performance: OpenMP achieves the highest speedups for both $N = 1000$ (7.68 \times) and $N = 900$ (7.73 \times), leveraging shared-memory parallelism to minimize overhead and fully utilize CPU cores.

Configuration	Run ID	Execution Time (s)	Speedup
Serial (Baseline)	7	2.628	1.00
OpenMP (8 threads)	21	0.342	7.68
MPI (8 ranks)	35	0.469	5.60

Table 1. Performance comparison for $N = 1000$, $T = 100$.

4.1.2 MPI Performance: MPI achieves lower speedups (5.60 \times for $N = 1000$, 4.54 \times for $N = 900$) due to communication overhead and load imbalance in distributed-memory parallelization.

Configuration	Run ID	Execution Time (s)	Speedup
Serial (Baseline)	18	41.377	1.00
OpenMP (8 threads)	32	5.354	7.73
MPI (8 ranks)	40	9.117	4.54

Table 2. Performance comparison for $N = 900$, $T = 2000$.

Fig. 5. Execution time is the fastest using OpenMP on a single node

4.2 Scalability Analysis

4.2.1 OpenMP Thread Scaling. OpenMP demonstrated strong scalability up to the number of physical cores. Execution times and speedups for different thread counts under $-O3$ optimization are shown below.

Threads	Execution Time (s)	Speedup	Efficiency (%)
1 (Serial)	2.628	1.00	100
2	0.738	3.56	178
4	0.395	6.65	166
8	0.342	7.68	96
12	0.349	7.53	63

Table 3. OpenMP scalability for $N = 1000$, $T = 100$.

Threads	Execution Time (s)	Speedup	Efficiency (%)
1 (Serial)	41.377	1.00	100
2	11.797	3.51	176
4	6.448	6.42	161
8	5.354	7.73	97
12	6.050	6.84	57

Table 4. OpenMP scalability for $N = 900$, $T = 2000$.

4.2.2 MPI Rank Scaling. MPI performance improved with rank count up to a point but suffered from diminishing returns due to communication overhead.

4.2.3 Key Observations.

- **OpenMP:** Performance scales efficiently up to 8 threads, achieving high speedup and efficiency. Beyond 8 threads, oversubscription results in diminishing returns due to hyper-threading and synchronization overhead.

Ranks	Execution Time (s)	Speedup	Efficiency (%)
1 (Serial)	2.628	1.00	100
2	1.317	2.00	100
4	0.493	5.33	133
8	0.469	5.60	70
12	0.548	4.80	40

 Table 5. MPI scalability for $N = 1000, T = 100$.

Ranks	Execution Time (s)	Speedup	Efficiency (%)
1 (Serial)	41.377	1.00	100
2	21.746	1.90	95
4	8.087	5.12	128
8	9.117	4.54	57
12	7.737	5.35	44

 Table 6. MPI scalability for $N = 900, T = 2000$.

- **MPI:** MPI scales well up to 4 ranks but suffers from reduced efficiency beyond that due to communication overhead and load imbalance. Larger datasets show similar trends but with higher baseline execution times.

Fig. 6. OpenMP scales efficiently to cores, while MPI is limited by communication overhead

5 Bottlenecks and Challenges

The N-body simulation faces several performance and scalability challenges:

- **Exponential Workload:** The simulation's $O(N^2)$ complexity causes the workload to grow quadratically. For example, Run 7 ($N = 1000, T = 100$) required 2.628 s, while Run 18 ($N = 900, T = 2000$) increased to 41.377 s, illustrating the rapid rise in execution times.
- **Load Imbalance in MPI:** Uneven workload distribution among ranks introduces inefficiencies. For instance, Run 35 (8 ranks) achieved 0.469 s, but increasing to 9 ranks in Run 36 resulted in 0.548 s due to added communication overhead.
- **OpenMP Overhead:** Performance plateaus beyond the number of physical cores. Run 21 (8 threads) achieved 0.342 s,

while Run 22 (12 threads) slightly increased to 0.349 s, reflecting diminishing returns from hyper-threading and resource contention.

- **Synchronization Costs:** Synchronization in parallel loops limits scalability. For example, Runs 19–22 showed negligible improvements beyond 8 threads, with synchronization overhead outweighing performance gains.
- **Vectorization Constraints:** Loop dependencies restrict effective SIMD utilization. Run 3 ($-O2$) required 2.887 s, while vectorization in Run 6 reduced this modestly to 2.683 s, a gain of just $\sim 7\%$.

6 Conclusion

6.1 Summary of Findings

Optimization of the N-body simulation delivered significant performance improvements:

- **Compiler Optimizations:** Transitioning from $-O0$ to $-O1$ significantly reduced runtime, achieving speedups of up to 4.88 \times . Higher optimization levels ($-O2, -O3$) provided diminishing returns.
- **Auto-Vectorization:** Modest improvements were observed, with a maximum speedup of 1.14 \times for $N = 500$. Gains were limited by data dependencies in nested loops.
- **OpenMP Multi-threading:** Delivered speedups of up to 7.73 \times for $N = 900$ using 8 threads. Performance plateaued beyond physical cores due to contention and hyper-threading inefficiencies.
- **MPI Parallelization:** Achieved optimal speedups of 5.6 \times for $N = 1000$ with 4–8 ranks, but scalability was constrained by communication overhead and workload imbalance.
- **Hybrid MPI-OpenMP:** The hybrid approach offered no additional benefits due to resource contention and synchronization overheads.
- **Scalability:** The $O(N^2)$ complexity limited scalability. OpenMP remained efficient for larger N , but algorithmic bottlenecks constrained further improvements.

6.2 Future Work

To address current performance bottlenecks and enhance scalability, the following strategies are recommended:

- **Algorithmic Improvements:** Implement efficient algorithms like Barnes-Hut or Fast Multipole Methods to reduce complexity from $O(N^2)$ to $O(N \log N)$. [6]
- **Advanced Parallelization:** Leverage GPU acceleration and optimized data structures to further enhance parallel performance. [7]
- **Distributed MPI:** Scale MPI across clusters to utilize additional computational resources, reduce communication overhead, and improve load balancing with high-speed interconnects.
- **Memory Optimization:** Optimize memory access patterns and reduce synchronization overhead to improve efficiency in larger simulations.

References

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A Appendix

Parameter	Details
Architecture	x86_64
CPU Op-mode(s)	32-bit, 64-bit
Address Sizes	39 bits physical, 48 bits virtual
Byte Order	Little Endian
CPU(s)	12
Online CPU(s) List	0-11
Vendor ID	GenuineIntel
Model Name	13th Gen Intel® Core™ i5-13420H
CPU Family	6
Model	186
Threads per Core	2
Cores per Socket	8
Socket(s)	1
Stepping	2
CPU Max Frequency	4600.0000 MHz
CPU Min Frequency	400.0000 MHz
Scaling MHz	54%
BogoMIPS	5222.40
L1d Cache	320 KiB (8 instances)
L1i Cache	384 KiB (8 instances)
L2 Cache	7 MiB (5 instances)
L3 Cache	12 MiB (1 instance)
NUMA Node(s)	1
NUMA Node0 CPU(s)	0-11
Virtualization	VT-x

Table 7. CPU Information for 13th Gen Intel Core i5-13420H.

RUN ID	TTR (s)	Threads	O Flag	Vectorised	MPI Ranks	(t)	(dt)	(T)	(N)
1	16.897692	-	O0	No	-	0	0.1	100	1000
2	3.461601	-	O1	No	-	0	0.1	100	1000
3	2.886775	-	O2	No	-	0	0.1	100	1000
4	2.846360	-	O3	No	-	0	0.1	100	1000
5	3.378130	-	O1	Yes	-	0	0.1	100	1000
6	2.683350	-	O2	Yes	-	0	0.1	100	1000
7	2.628334	-	O3	Yes	-	0	0.1	100	1000
8	2.150109	-	O0	No	-	0	0.1	50	500
9	0.461240	-	O1	No	-	0	0.1	50	500
10	0.371506	-	O2	No	-	0	0.1	50	500
11	0.389878	-	O3	No	-	0	0.1	50	500
12	0.427308	-	O1	Yes	-	0	0.1	50	500
13	0.344306	-	O2	Yes	-	0	0.1	50	500
14	0.340625	-	O3	Yes	-	0	0.1	50	500
15	269.980	-	O0	No	-	0	0.1	2000	900
16	54.090544	-	O1	Yes	-	0	0.1	2000	900
17	41.822200	-	O2	Yes	-	0	0.1	2000	900
18	41.377000	-	O3	Yes	-	0	0.1	2000	900
19	0.737657	2	O3	No	-	0	0.1	100	1000
20	0.395019	4	O3	No	-	0	0.1	100	1000
21	0.341905	8	O3	No	-	0	0.1	100	1000
22	0.349071	12	O3	No	-	0	0.1	100	1000
23	11.797377	2	O3	No	-	0	0.1	2000	900
24	6.447804	4	O3	No	-	0	0.1	2000	900
25	6.136276	8	O3	No	-	0	0.1	2000	900
26	6.050254	12	O3	No	-	0	0.1	2000	900
27	0.322106	8	O3	Yes	-	0	0.1	100	1000
28	0.425068	8	O1	Yes	-	0	0.1	100	1000
29	0.432831	8	O1	No	-	0	0.1	100	1000
30	7.112487	8	O1	No	-	0	0.1	2000	900
31	6.968547	8	O1	Yes	-	0	0.1	2000	900
32	5.353720	8	O3	Yes	-	0	0.1	2000	900
33	1.316918	-	O3	Yes	2	0	0.1	100	1000
34	0.492942	-	O3	Yes	4	0	0.1	100	1000
35	0.469445	-	O3	Yes	8	0	0.1	100	1000
36	0.547812	-	O3	Yes	9	0	0.1	100	1000
37	0.897167	-	O3	Yes	12	0	0.1	100	1000
38	21.745740	-	O3	Yes	2	0	0.1	2000	900
39	8.086790	-	O3	Yes	4	0	0.1	2000	900
40	9.117396	-	O3	Yes	8	0	0.1	2000	900
41	7.519226	-	O3	Yes	9	0	0.1	2000	900
42	7.736674	-	O3	Yes	12	0	0.1	2000	900
43	55.294730	-	O1	No	-	0	0.1	2000	900
44	41.822200	-	O2	No	-	0	0.1	2000	900
45	42.547801	-	O3	No	-	0	0.1	2000	900

Table 8. Log data for various runs with additional information